

LEGAL BASIS OF PREVENTING AND FIGHTING CORRUPTION IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article provides an explanation of the state policy aimed at preventing and fighting corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan, normative legal documents based on international law and defining the uncompromising fight against corruption. Similarly, the United Nations Convention Against Corruption and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On fighting corruption” were analyzed.

Key words: corruption, UN Convention Against Corruption, Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On fighting corruption”, Anti-Corruption Agency.

Аннотация: В данной статье дается разъяснение государственной политики, направленной на предупреждение и борьбу с коррупцией в Республике Узбекистан, нормативно-правовые документы, основанные на международном праве и определяющие бескомпромиссную борьбу с коррупцией. Аналогичным образом были проанализированы Конвенция ООН против коррупции и Закон Республики Узбекистан «О борьбе с коррупцией».

Ключевые слова: коррупция, Конвенция ООН против коррупции, Закон Республики Узбекистан «О борьбе с коррупцией», Агентство по борьбе с коррупцией.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston Respublikasida korrupsiyani oldini olish va unga qarshi kurashishga qaratilgan davlat siyosati, xalqaro huquq normalariga asoslangan va korrupsiyaga qarshi murosasiz kurashishni belgilab beruvchi normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar haqida tushuntirish berildi. Shunindek, Birlashgan Millatlar Tashkiloti tomonidan qabul qilingan “Korrupsiyaga qarshi

kurashish konvensiyasi” hamda O‘zbekiston Respublikasining “Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashish to‘g‘risida”gi Qonuni tahlil etildi.

Kalit so‘zlar: korrupsiya, BMT “Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashish konvensiyasi”, O‘zbekiston Respublikasining “Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashish to‘g‘risida”gi Qonuni , Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashish agentligi.

Today, almost all countries of the world are seriously struggling with corruption, which is one of the most urgent problems. Unfortunately, this problem has not bypassed the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is taking steps towards democratic reforms. It is no exaggeration to say that corruption is one of the biggest problems preventing the rapid development of our country. Of course, large-scale reforms aimed at preventing corruption are being implemented in our country and legal mechanisms are being developed. Before discussing the legal basis of preventing and fighting corruption, it would be appropriate to define the concept of corruption itself.

According to the legal encyclopedia, "the word corruption is derived from the Latin word ``corruptio", which means bribery, bribery - that is, a socially dangerous phenomenon in the field of politics and state administration, which allows individuals or legal entities to illegally acquire material and other wealth and benefits by persons who have the authority to perform state functions (or are equal to them)."¹As mentioned above, corruption has a negative impact not only on the country's politics and state administration, but also on the economy of that country, its influence in the world, and also on the moral and moral influence of the society. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov, also commented on the negative consequences of corruption and wrote in one of his books, "...crime and corruption destroy moral foundations of society. It destroys the civil status of the members of society. It creates conditions for the emergence

¹ Legal encyclopedia of Uzbekistan / Responsible for publication R.A. Muhitdinov and others; responsible editor N. Toychiyev. - T.; Adolat, 2009. - p. 264

of a negative attitude to the changes being implemented,"² he wrote. Yes, as the First President noted, corruption is such a big problem that as long as this scourge exists, any reforms implemented for the development of the country will fail, and as a result, distrust and negative attitude towards them will be formed among citizens. It would not be wrong to say that the current President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev is logically continuing the policy of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov to fight against corruption and taking it to a new level. For example, in 2016, our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the joint session of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, said that "we need to take strict measures to fight corruption, committing various crimes and other violations in our society, to prevent them, and to enforce the requirements of the law that punishment for crime is inevitable"³ so he emphasized the need to put an end to corrupt situations. Yes, the scope of dangerous social consequences caused by corruption is very wide. Among other things, R. Altiyev stated that "...corruption, first of all, hinders the provision of human rights and causes social inequality. "It leads to the decrease of the free-market economy and in the standard of living"⁴ and these are also deeply important.

In order to prevent the negative consequences mentioned above, Uzbekistan, following the democratic path, as an equal member of the world community, on July 7, 2008, joined the United Nations Convention against Corruption, adopted in New York on October 31, 2003. This convention, which consists of a total of 8 chapters and 71 articles, provides for the goals of preventing and fighting corruption, measures to prevent corruption and mechanisms for their implementation, as well as issues of mutual cooperation between states. According to this convention, "each state party, in accordance with the basic principles of its legal system, develops and implements or maintains an effective and coordinated

² Karimov I.A. Uzbekistan on the threshold of the 21st century: threats to security, conditions of stability and guarantees of development. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 1997. - 89-p

³ Mirziyoyev Sh.M. We will build a free and prosperous, democratic state of Uzbekistan together with our brave and noble people - T.: "Uzbekistan", 2016. p. 10.

⁴ R. Altiyev Important reforms in the fight against corruption today - a collection of materials of the republican scientific and practical seminar on the topic "Corruption: law and responsibility". TDYU, 2017, p-99

anti-corruption policy that promotes public participation and reflects the principles of law and order, public affairs and public property management, honesty and integrity, transparency and accountability."⁵ In order to ensure the implementation of this international norm specified in the Convention, several works have been carried out in our country over the past years. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption" adopted on January 3, 2017 can be cited as the most striking example. The adoption of this law determined the legal basis for preventing and fighting corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Article 3 of this law defined the concept of corruption, and according to it, corruption is "illegal use of a person's position or official position for the purpose of obtaining material or immaterial benefit for personal interests or the interests of other persons, as well as unlawful presentation of such a name."⁶ To put it simply, abuse of authority by a person for material or immaterial benefit creates corruption. Also, according to the above-mentioned law, the main principles of the fight against corruption were defined, such as legality, openness and transparency, cooperation between the state and civil society, the priority of measures to prevent corruption, and the inevitability of responsibility. According to this law, state bodies such as the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Department for Combating Economic Crimes under the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan were designated as state bodies carrying out anti-corruption activities, and their powers in the field of combating corruption were determined separately. Although the above-mentioned bodies have achieved good results in the fight against corruption, and the level of corruption in our country has significantly decreased, there was a need to establish a single body that would constantly coordinate the activities of these state bodies. Due to this, the Anti-Corruption Agency was established on June 29, 2020 in accordance with the

⁵ https://www.unodc.org/documents/brussels/UN_Convention_Against_Corruption.pdf

⁶ <https://lex.uz/docs/-3088008> . The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption"

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the system of fighting corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan". "The agency is a state body specially authorized to formulate and implement state policy in the field of prevention and fight against corruption. The agency is subordinate to the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and is accountable to the chambers of the Oliy Majlis (parliament) of the Republic of Uzbekistan."⁷ After the establishment of this agency, in 2021, amendments and additions were made to the Law "On Combating Corruption". According to it, the interdepartmental anti-corruption commissions were reorganized into the National Anti-Corruption Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional councils as coordinating bodies involved in the fight against corruption in Article 8. Including, in Article 8¹ of the law, 12 main powers of the Anti-Corruption Agency in the field of anti-corruption were defined. Among these powers, the main ones are "formulation and implementation of the state policy in the field of prevention and fight against corruption, analysis of the efficiency of the system of anti-corruption examination of normative legal documents and their projects, submission of proposals for the improvement of this system, and submission of submissions that must be considered to stop or cancel the execution of the decisions of executive authorities and economic management bodies and their officials in cases where signs of corruption are detected."⁸

After Uzbekistan ratified the United Nations Convention on Combating Corruption in 2008, in addition to the Law "On Combating Corruption", more than 20 normative legal documents defining the criteria for preventing and fighting corruption in various fields were adopted, and some normative legal documents lost their force as a result of the improvement of legislation and the implementation of international standards into our legislation. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan", "On the approval of the regulation on the

⁷ <https://anticorruption.uz/uz/item/missiya>

⁸ <https://lex.uz/docs/-3088008> The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Corruption"

procedure for encouraging persons who have reported a crime related to corruption or otherwise assisted in the fight against corruption" Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On the approval of the regulation on the procedure for anti-corruption examination of regulatory legal documents and their drafts" the order of the Minister of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to further improve the activities of the Anti-Corruption Agency of the Republic of Uzbekistan" have raised the anti-corruption policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a new level.

In conclusion, we can say that in order to prevent and fight against corruption in the Republic of Uzbekistan, regulatory legal documents have been adopted that are in full compliance with international legislation and standards. Nevertheless, the indicators of corruption cases remain relatively high, in our opinion, due to insufficient implementation of these laws and legal documents. Because of this, prevention of corruption in our country and drastic fight against it should become the primary tasks not only of the responsible state bodies, but also of all our citizens, and it is necessary to work together to put an end to corrupt situations.

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